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TRANSLATION PROCESS IN LITERATURE DURING INDEPENDENCE PERIOD

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***Annotation:** Big country artistic system in the composition region literary environment too internal development laws own from the head forgives. Literary process common development principles welded poetic ring certain creative stylistic - formal research qualified perfection, talent level manifestation to be and artistic skill experience softening by means of aesthetic to value achieves. National independence spirituality in the chronicle to the hand included successes, reforms system in Karakalpakstan Uzbek literary life new to stage to raise strong the ground prepares.*

As a poet and writer, Ya. Kochkarov, who created very good works of art, is also known and famous for his significant works in the field of journalism. His journalistic articles and translations are regularly published in the prestigious publications of our Republic Literary critic G'.Mahmud "Yangiboy has enthusiasm and inner enthusiasm. Staying in Karakalpakstan, he wanders around Tashkent and Andijan, Fergana and Namangan, and does not rest. I consider it an incomparable quality that he finds creative people wherever he goes, talks with them, and is passionate about promoting them." 81he admits. Karakalpak writer, child of the people who has been introducing poets to Uzbeks, Uzbek writers and poets, scientists to the people of Karakalpak. His article "Sakkiz burgut syrati" is written about the famous artists of the Uzbek, Karakalpak, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Avar peoples, while the essay "Muattar Mehr" talks

about the ghazal poet F.Usman. Ya.Kochkarov's essay "A plane tree on the beach" is dedicated to the well-known scientist from Tortkol O.Khudoyberganov. It contains information about the famous people of Tortkol, the essay "Stars on the Moon" and the establishment of the State Award named after Zulfiya, information about the women of Zulfiyakhanim's contemporaries and creators, who met her directly, talked to her, and interacted with her at various conferences, from the eight sister and neighboring countries mentioned in the book gives Also, in the book "The World of a Wise Poet", he wrote a good essay about Ollobergan Polat, a famous children's poet from Khorezm, and in his largescale essays and essays, such as "Heroes of Ellikkala", "Aralboyi Azamatlari", he sheds light on the creative works of the children of this country. Ya. Kochkarov is a skilled journalist who has created mature examples in various genres of journalism.

M. Yusupova started her journalistic career very early. His journalistic article "Uzbek Momo" and his journalistic books "Tortkolim - Dur - Gulim" were published. These books contain articles and literary thoughts about achievements in every field of the district.

The poet's books "The Path of Love" (2006), "Taqlid Bitikari" (2021) were published. In the book "Destiny Letters" the thoughts of the poet during her life are summarized in the form of drops. B. Umarov wrote the foreword to the book: "You write sincerely from the heart with emotion. This - half victory! Poetry is an assistant of prose that clicks the necessary strings when the thoughts are not fully conveyed to the heart, to the top of the mind. Your appeal to the creator, your prayer is very bright.

The reader who reads the drops feels sincerity and great pain. This is the pain of self-awareness, the pain of humanity. Below we refer to M. Yusuf drops: It's like I'm another. The Munavvar that bothers me seems to leave his body like me for a week or 2-3 days... I'm sleeping peacefully and living peacefully... fate is over! This is your quiet silence before another test or exam a terrible scream, a roar, seems to be starting the ball. It is also known from history that decisive battles have started in the wake of silence. Who will win the decisive battle? Some kind of power or mine?!

Don't leave me

Let's live as a union.

Our service is excellent.

In the country where you are dying...

Life has everything. And again created in pairs. For example, black and white, sin and reward, long and short, night and day, sun and moon etc. Merciful breath and satanic lust, good and evil are the constant companions of man.

They are sleeping and living... Let them open their eyes wider. Around only the soul of the man who feels that all the beauties are for him will live forever.

A childhood relationship found you. It's like I was born with you.

I live with

You. With you.

Even at the last moment, stay with me, Lord.

The author's poems are closely connected with the idea of trust in the Creator, his attitude to life, conclusions, and thoughts through life events and pictures.

In the science of literary studies, translation is one of the most convenient forms of literary communication. Literature is also enriched through translations. In particular, since the Karakalpak language and Uzbek languages are close to each other, it is convenient to use word-to-word translation as much as possible while preserving the content. In this case, not so big defects are noticeable. Mirtemir paid great attention to the issue of translation in his friendly relations with Karakalpak literature. It is known that he translated the works of Berdaq, the Karakalpak folk epic "Kirqqiz". If the translator treats the literature of that nation with respect, if he loves to study the language of that nation, he will achieve a smooth translation. From this point of view, the preservation of originality, genre features, unchanged description of the lyrical hero's psychology should not be ignored in the translation.

We can see that in the years of independence of Karakalpakstan, significant work was done in the field of translation studies, mature examples of translations from Uzbek to Karakalpak, from Karakalpak to Uzbek, and from Russian to Uzbek were created.

Especially in the work of G.Matyokubova and Ya.Kochkarov, who are equally creative in two languages, we often find such translations.

Spreading my dream to the whole world,
I gave my being too sweet hopes,
I think: What will cast a shadow on them.
Beauty - smile label,
Or a slave to tortured passion,
As you read this humble line,
They share their secret sorrow.
My heart is full of excitement...84

As we can see, the poet managed to preserve the content and form of the poem as it was originally. In these verses, the poet believes that sweet dreams and hopes make the whole world beautiful, and nothing can overshadow the full existence of dreams. The poet's heart full of hopes indicates that he is full of good things. A person who reads these lines will be enchanted with the poet's heart full of excitement. Because the person who reads the poem finds the secrets of his heart in these lines. For this reason, such verses are close to the heart of the reader, not only the poet himself. We can say that the poem "Sadness" written by A. Fet is also well translated:

Everywhere in the gray, gloomy sky,
Let the autumn wind blow the purple cloud.
The rain hits the glass like stones,
A storm swirls over the open field.
Golden leaves disturb the peace of the garden,
Hazans build a bonfire in front of me.
Then I will be like autumn,
Endless sadness fills my heart.

The image of nature in the poem is enriched with symbols such as gray, autumn, cloud, storm, haze. Symbolism is strong in A.Fet's work, the grayness of the sky, the play of clouds, and the sound of rain hitting the glass like a stone; embody the vivid

image of the autumn season before your eyes. It is natural that the leaves falling like gold, the khazans shimmering creating a fiery beautiful appearance, remind that human life also has a khazan season. In the poem, these situations show the human spirit in front of your eyes, skillfully using the means of artistic imagery.

The poet has successfully translated the poems of many Karakalpak poets into Uzbek. In particular, we will get acquainted with the translations into Uzbek of poems from the collection "My Windows" by K. Karimov:

When you trample your soil in bits and pieces,
The land of birth! Your love, your value is unknown.
But when I walk away from your warm embrace,
My eyelashes do not hang at all from longing.
I walked the fields, climbed the mountains,
I crossed the rivers to drink water.
I saw orchards with ripe fruit,
But your love was drawn to him.

Every verse of this poem written by K.Karimov was translated very skillfully by the poetess. The original content of the poem has been preserved, the words are chosen very correctly, no fault can be found in any of its lines. He translates the beautiful lines from the poet's poem "Maqsad" as follows:

I asked the river: "Is your goal rare?"
"I will flow in the bosom of rivers."
I asked the birds: "Is your goal rare?"
"I fly freely and flap my wings."
I asked the mountains: "Is your goal rare?"
"High and high to block the cloud"
I asked the roads: "Is your goal rare?"
"Go through the desert, fields, and mountains."85

In this poem, the poet tried to keep the content of each verse as it was originally. He was able to choose the words exactly according to the content.

Translations also played an important role in Ya.Kochkharov's work. The writer created very beautiful translations from Uzbek, Russian, and Karakalpak languages. In particular, he translated into Uzbek the novels of S.Aleksievich "War is a foreign image of a woman" and V.Sumin's "The Last and First Subhidam". Below we will review and analyze the translator's translations from Karakalpak to Uzbek. The poet has a lot of translations of works of Karakalpak poets. One of them is the poem "Landscapes of Bukhara" by U.Khojanov, and we will try to analyze the Uzbek translation of the poem:

The old minor of Bukhara,
A monkey stands out from all of them.
Two mosques are next to each other,
Zarbof wears a tunic.
Years after years passed,
The king came and went.
One trip to the emir,
It was presented in this way.
- How about we start something,

Summary:

In the years of independence, in the literary environment of the region, the desire to freely reflect the feelings of trust and faith in the Creator of the experiences of the human heart increased, and beautiful examples were created in poetic forms;

In the period of independence, the prose genres of the region's literature improved significantly, expanded the objects of artistic images, assimilated the important features of artistic genres into their nature, and the creators common one topic Island topic reflection to continue scientific based on;

Changes in the quality of the prose of the independence period are scientific based on;

Independence period to literature special of subjects the variety of genres rich going, different genre works samples created scientific analyses based on proven.

Referenses used list

1. Kochkharov Ya. Welcome to Khorezm. - T.: "New century generation", 2010 - 175 p.
2. Akhmedov M. In Kiprigin hanging standing my It's my soul ... Nukus . "Karakalpakstan", 1995.-120 p
3. Yusufova M. Blooming love or destiny letters. Urganch. "Youth of Khorezm", 2021. -115 p